

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PEDIATRIC DENTAL ANESTHESIA GUIDELINE
DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION
IN AN AMBULATORY CENTER

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Poor dentition has been linked to below average academic performance, maladjusted psychosocial behavior, and overall decreased physical health in school aged children. For children requiring multiple dental procedures and those who are uncooperative or anxious, sedation and general anesthesia may be necessary.

When conventional treatment in the dental office is not possible, children are referred to outpatient facilities for conscious sedation or general anesthesia. Patient safety and the administration of anesthesia with cautious oversight among this population can be challenging. Thus, the purpose of this project was to develop evidence-based pediatric dental anesthesia clinical practice guidelines for an ambulatory surgery center in the inland area of Southern California.

An expert panel (Delphi method) was recruited to participate in the development and evaluation of pediatric dental anesthesia outpatient guidelines. This expert panel included a physician anesthesiologist, a dental anesthesiologist, certified nurse anesthetists, and advanced practice registered nurses working in pediatric dental surgery centers. The expert panel participated in three rounds of review and revision of the guidelines using the Delphi method until 100% consensus was reached in the third round.

The guidelines were developed based on evidence-based research findings and divided into four sections: (a) pre-procedural assessment phone evaluation and education; (b) informed consent checklist including the key elements of an informed consent/pre-

procedural assessment for the day of surgery checklist; (c) critical event training and curriculum, quality management checklist for root cause analysis, and (d) triage to a higher level of care pathways. Triage pathways are airway fires, aspiration, anaphylaxis, malignant hyperthermia, and sustained hypoxia.

Evidence-based research supports clinical practice guidelines to improve patient outcome. The Plan, Do, Study, Act framework was utilized in the development of these guidelines. A review of the literature supported the development of guidelines in 4 areas. The Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guidelines (PDAG) were validated as reliable by a panel of experts. In June 2019, the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) updated its statement on pediatric dental sedation. The AAP's 2019 recommendation includes the need for a trained anesthesia provider to be present to monitor a child during the administration of an anesthetic. Dissemination of the PDAG's by the primary author initially occurred at the California Association of Nurse Anesthetists in October of 2019. Implementation of the guidelines will occur by June 2020 at a pediatric dental ambulatory center in the Inland Empire. The author is in the process of seeking funding from the American Association of Nurse Anesthetists Foundation (aana.com), a national organization, for the purpose of developing a pediatric dental anesthesia guideline application for handheld mobile devices. The continued vision of the primary author is to disseminate PDAG's locally as well as nationally to gain professional and public awareness to improve the practice of pediatric dental anesthesia.

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BACKGROUND

In school-age children, poor dentition has been linked to below average academic performance, maladjusted psychosocial behavior, and overall decreased physical health (Guarnizo-Herreno & Wehby, 2012). Dental caries are five times more likely to occur in children ages 5 to 17 than a diagnosis of asthma (Sen et al., 2013). Nationally, Achembong et al. (2014) noted in their ecologic study that untreated caries was ranked tenth out of 295 diseases and injuries afflicting children. Overall, untreated dental disease can lead to children's decreased quality of life (Achembong, Kranz, & Rozier, 2014).

For children requiring multiple dental procedures, sedation and general anesthesia may become necessary. Sedation and general anesthesia might also be required for uncooperative and anxious children who undergo dental examinations and preventative care (Spera, Saxen, Yepes, Jones, & Sanders, 2017). The anesthetic agents needed to perform dental examinations and procedures requiring sedation are currently being administered in hospitals, office-based practices, and outpatient surgery centers.

Outpatient procedures have grown in number. In 1984, the number of outpatient procedures performed was approximately 400,000. By the year 2000, the number had grown to over 8.3 billion and continues to increase (Spera et al., 2017). This increase has been caused, in part, by the fact that hospital-based treatment for patients is costly. Delayed availability and access to hospital-based procedures are associated with postponed treatment. Therefore, more children experience anesthesia outside of the hospital for minor procedures and diagnostic treatments (Spera et al., 2017).

Statistics related to pediatric dental patients requiring anesthesia in outpatient facilities, including office-based practice, are not tracked locally, statewide, or nationally (The Dental Board of California, 2016). The California Dental Board requires its members to report all mortalities related to dental procedures as well as hospitalizations longer than 24 hours. The Dental Board of California reported that, from January 1, 2010, to December 31, 2015, the board was notified of nine pediatric deaths associated with dental procedures. In the same 6-year period, the board was notified of 45 hospitalizations. Due to the absence of a national reporting database for anesthesia-related morbidity and mortality, it is difficult to monitor untoward outcomes (Lee et al., 2017).

Treatment for dental rehabilitation in children under the age of 18 can be challenging. When conventional methods of treatment in the dental office are not possible, children are often referred to outpatient facilities for conscious sedation or general anesthesia to safely complete the necessary dental treatment (Spera et al., 2017). Methods of treatment for these children include dental X-rays and examinations. Based on the examination results, rehabilitation treatment is administered by pediatric dentists. These procedures can include dental decay removal, fillings, stainless steel crown placement, and teeth extraction.

Patient safety and the administration of anesthesia with cautious oversight among this population can be challenging. Anesthesia complications in outpatient facilities are rare but do exist. Aspiration, airway fire, and anaphylaxis are some of these rare events (Cote & Wilson, 2016). The most common complication associated with children under the influence of sedation and general anesthesia is respiratory compromise (Spera et al.,

2017). However, when guidelines are in place and followed, anesthesia risks are minimized (American Association of Nurse Anesthetists, 2017).

The pediatric airway anatomy is different from that of an adult. A child's trachea is narrow and any amount of swelling or irritation can subject the child to several complications in the perioperative period. Some of these complications are laryngospasm, bronchospasm, airway obstruction, and hypoxia.

The failure to recognize at-risk patient situations or unforeseen events can lead to catastrophic events if not treated early and appropriately. In outpatient facilities, an ineffective resuscitative measure or an inappropriate intervention is the primary reason for an adverse outcome (Cote & Wilson, 2016). The utilization of evidence-based practice guidelines and best practice standards of care can reduce mortality and morbidity in pediatric dental patients receiving anesthesia (Spera et al., 2017).

Problem Statement

The author is employed as a CRNA at an outpatient surgery center in Southern California where children, 18 months to 11 years of age, receive dental treatment while under anesthesia. Their dental treatments range from common cleaning and sealant placement to extractions. Presently, the surgery center is not utilizing formal, standardized guidelines as a written plan of care for anesthetized patients. The care of each patient is based on the individual anesthesia provider's plan of care. Although anesthesia complications in the children served in this clinic are rare, continued efforts to improve patient care are important. There is strong evidence-based research support for the use of clinical practice safety guidelines when administering anesthesia to pediatric patients (American Academy of Pediatrics [AAP], 2016). The author and her colleagues

agree that developing a set of written standardized guidelines for their practice setting is a needed quality improvement measure.

Purpose of the Project

The purpose of this project was to develop and evaluate guidelines for anesthesia practice in the pediatric dental outpatient setting that were agreed upon by an expert panel. The development of these guideline involved a review of the literature, including an assessment of the quality of the evidence according to its strength and significance of the results. Due to the limited numbers of randomized control studies available for some of the topics discussed, an expert panel (Delphi Method) was utilized. This panel included physician anesthesiologists, a dental anesthesiologist, certified nurse anesthetists, and advanced practice registered nurses in a pediatric dental surgery center.

The author drafted pediatric dental anesthesia safety guidelines based on her literature review. She then identified a panel of experts to participate in a modified Delphi Method to critique and modify the draft guidelines until consensus was reached as to their benefit in improving safe delivery of anesthesia to children in ambulatory care settings. Implementation and dissemination of the guidelines developed will be conducted in the second phase of this project. Evaluation of the assessment tools is to be performed by comparing data collected using the assessment checklist prior to surgery with data reported using the same checklist the day of surgery. Evaluation of appropriate triage to a higher level of care will be audited on a continuous basis. Critical events training will be evaluated by a pre-test and post-test and routinely conducted based on a center's agreed upon timeframe. The first phase of this project (pediatric dental anesthesia guidelines) was completed January 2020 (Appendix A). The second phase of

implementation, evaluation, and dissemination of outcome findings will be conducted post DNP degree completion in May 2020.

Supporting Framework

A theoretical framework provides a method of organizing the process of planning, implementing and evaluating projects for quality improvement. It is important to choose a framework suited to a specific quality improvement (QI) project. Understanding the quality care problem, utilizing evidence-based practice, and selecting an appropriate framework are critical to the success of an improvement project (Schaffer, Sandau, & Deidrick, 2013).

Plan Do Study Act

The Plan Do Study Act (PDSA) cycle is a rapid improvement framework that allows for planning, implementing, measuring, and modifying the process of improvement (Figure 1). Utilization of the PDSA enables an improvement project to be implemented in a short period of time by adapting and repeating the cycle as necessary for the desired improvement outcome. The PDSA cycle moves forward quickly. The cycle process evolves by either being adapted, abandoned, or adopted (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2019).

The PDSA cycle was developed by Dr. W. Edwards Deming. PDSA is a modification of a framework introduced to Dr. Deming by his mentor, Dr. Walter Shewhart. Dr. Shewhart developed a method of improvement that utilized the principle of Plan Do Check Act (PDCA). Dr. Deming hypothesized that the check step of PDCA would slow down the progress of the cycle. By replacing the check step with the study step, this re-envisioned cycle allowed the investigators to evaluate the data obtained from

small tests of change and provide the momentum needed to move rapidly toward adapting, abandoning, or adopting the plan (The W. Edwards Deming Institute, 2019).

Plan. Organizing a project based on the PDSA cycle begins with planning and setting clear objectives for the project. This is called the *plan* stage. Once a team of stakeholders for the project is identified, the initial planning stage of the improvement process begins. A purpose statement (aim statement) is developed. During the planning stage, the team brainstorms answers to the following questions: What are the QI goals? How will we know if a change has been made? If there is a change, is it an improvement? How can we change the process to create an improvement? Data collection methods are developed in this step of the cycle. It is important to identify which stakeholders will accomplish specific tasks needed for the implementation of the collection process (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Do. The second step in the cycle is the *do* phase. This step includes carrying out the proposed plan. The accuracy of this step is important because it helps define the validity of the process. Accurate execution of the plan and meticulous data collection are vital to the analysis of the data (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Study. The *study* step is undertaken by analyzing and evaluating the data collected in the *do* step. Knowledge gained in the study step affects the decisions to be made in the next step, *act* (Provost & Murray, 2011).

Act. *Act* is the step where the decision to adapt, adopt, or abandon the test of change takes place. Multiple cycles of PDSA can lead to accumulation of knowledge critical for increasing quality of care. Refining, adapting, or modifying the plan decreases the risk of failure in the implementation of the QI project.

Figure 1. PDSA Cycle from “The Improvement Guide,” by G. J. Langley, R. D. Moen, K. M. Nolan, T. W. Nolan, C. L. Norman, and L. P. Provost, 2009. Copyright 2009 by Gerald J. Langley, Ronald D. Moen, Kevin M. Nolan, Thomas W. Nolan, Clifford L. Norman, and Lloyd P. Provost. Reprinted with permission.

Plan Do Study Act Literature Review

PDSA to implement a critical care pain tool. Mascarenhas et al. (2018) utilized the PDSA framework to implement an observational tool for identifying pain in critical care patients. This project’s population was unable to self-report pain due to the severity of their illness and being ventilator dependent. The *plan* step was organized by stakeholders consisting of nurses, consultants, a pharmacy lead, and a lead physiotherapist. They identified a measurable aim, planned for data collection, collected and analyzed the data, and then used this knowledge to create additional cycles of PDSA. They conducted three PDSA cycles. The lessons learned from each cycle determined the need for adapting the next cycle of change. The ability to rapidly adapt the PDSA

framework allowed for the success of the project. The process of quick lessons learned empowered the team to communicate their concerns for the safe administration of narcotics to this unique population. The PDSA cycle allowed for small scale positive changes which were important considerations in the care of this population of critical patients. Small changes minimized the risks to these patients who tended to be more sensitive to narcotics.

The QI team used the PDSA cycle to implement an observational tool for assessment of pain in patients unable to communicate their pain (Mascarenhas et al., 2018). The staff members' unwillingness to engage in the change process, frustration from the constant change process, and lack of available resources to collect data were barriers acknowledged by the authors. After consideration of the barriers, the team implemented an online tool to simplify the documentation process. Reported benefits included finding that patients ultimately were more comfortable and less sedated. The patients were then able to participate in their own care.

PDSA to reduce single-dose medication vial use for multiple pediatric patients. In the operating room, single-dose and multidose fentanyl vials are available for use by anesthesia providers. Using single-dose vials for multiple patients violates the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2012) guidelines for single-use vials. Buck, Subramanyam, and Varughese (2015) organized a QI team consisting of anesthesia providers, a QI lead, and an employee from the pharmacy. The Model for Improvement, including the PDSA cycle, was the framework chosen by the stakeholders to implement the QI project. During the *plan* step, the team identified key drivers and developed the aim statement. In each of the multiple cycles of PDSA, the team asked the question,

what, who, where, and when? The *do* step involved both qualitative and quantitative data collection. The primary measure was the percentage of pediatric patients receiving fentanyl from a previously used vial. The goal was to reduce the baseline data by one-half. The qualitative data collected were narrative responses in emails to the QI team who solicited feedback from anesthesia providers. The utilization and analysis of run charts enabled the team to move to the next step, *study*. The first study cycle identified wasting excessive medication from single-dose vials as time-consuming. This led the team to the next step, *act*, and to adapt the plan to have the pharmacy allocate smaller syringes of fentanyl. This project utilized multiple PDSA cycles. The authors reported a successful project outcome based on a reduction in the multiuse of single-dose vials (Buck et al., 2015).

Application of the PDSA framework for guideline development in the DNP project. The utilization of the PDSA cycle is appropriate for developing and evaluating guidelines (Figure 2). The planning cycle for the guidelines' development component that took place in this first phase of the project included identifying the process, outcome, and balancing measures for developing guidelines: preoperative instructions, an anesthesia assessment tool linked to consent for anesthesia, critical events training, and a quality management tool for root cause analysis. The study, act and adapt portion was conducted during the evaluation of the guidelines utilizing the expert panel and Delphi survey. The proposed second phase of this project will begin with the PDSA cycle starting over again in subsequent iterations of this ongoing process post doctorate. Depending on the need to adapt, abandon, or adopt this initial process, the cycles continue until completion of the second phase of the project.

Figure 2. Adapted PDSA Cycle from “The Improvement Guide” by G. J. Langley, R. D. Moen, K. M. Nolan, T. W. Nolan, C.L. Norman, and L. P. Provost. Copyright 2009 by Gerald J. Langley, Ronald D. Moen, Kevin M. Nolan, Thomas W. Nolan, Clifford L. Norman, and Lloyd P. Provost. Reprinted with permission.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Overview

A literature review is a systematic method of searching databases for literature about the topic of interest. A well-defined systematic review decreases bias and adds validity to a scholarly project. Searching specific databases and utilizing words or terms related to the topic can assist in identifying gaps in the literature as well as gathering the newest information regarding the subject of interest and managing the volume of information available (Rouch, 2019).

Inclusion criteria for the literature review were peer-reviewed articles, studies, and journals published in English between the years of 2014 and 2019. PubMed, Google scholar CINAHL, IHI, and One Search databases were used to conduct the literature review. The search terms were PDSA and guidelines, PDSA and procedural sedation, PDSA and pediatrics, PDSA and anesthesia, dental procedural sedation, pediatric anesthesia, guidelines, pediatric airway physiology, safety in anesthesia, ambulatory surgical centers, just culture, and anesthesia guidelines. The secondary search terms were anesthesia preoperative assessment, just culture, just culture in health care, anesthesia debriefing, quality management tools, anesthesia simulation, and critical event training. Other topics that were included in the search terms included practice guidelines and policies and safety in dental outpatient settings (Appendix B).

The purpose of this project was to develop and evaluate evidence-based anesthesia practice guidelines for an outpatient pediatric dental practice. Evidence-based practice is based on studies that are categorized into different grades of evidence. The tool for evidence grading of assessment utilized in this review of the literature (ROL) is

the Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice (JHNEBP) (Johns Hopkins Center for Evidence-Based Practice, 2017). These grades are based on the strength of evidence and the significance of the results. The grading system ranges from 1-5 and A-C in ranking. Grades 1 and A are the highest levels of studies (Appendix C). Randomized control trials and meta-analysis reviews are in the category of the highest level of evidence (Bootland, Coughlan, Galloway, Goubet, & McWhirter, 2017).

The ROL found a limited number of studies. The review also revealed a gap in the literature for unbiased, high-level systematic reviews and meta-analyses. The majority of studies were Grade 1 and Grade 4 based on the JHNEBP.

Informed Consent

Informed consent for pediatric patients can be complex. A parent or guardian is needed to provide consent for patients under the age of 18 unless the patient is emancipated. Informed consent is defined by law as full informational disclosure of risks for the interventions to be provided (AAP, 2016). Providing answers and education to the surrogate is the ethical responsibility of the provider performing that intervention. Firdouse, Wajchandler, Koyle, and Fecteau (2017) and Gentry, Lepere, and Opel (2017) found limited data related to elements necessary to gain consent among the pediatric population. Furthermore, the lack of a standardized process was associated with deficits in informed consent such as incorrect patient consented for a procedure or the incorrect location of the operative site identified on the consent form (Firdouse et al., 2017). These deficits can lead to critical events related to the wrong patient and the wrong procedure (Oak, Dave, & Parelkar, 2015).

Gentry et al. (2015) identified components of informed consent related to parental recall. Although these researchers noted there was parental recall related to the consent process, this did not improve parental understanding of the intervention to which the parent gave consent. The recommendation of the researchers was to conduct a presurgical discussion of anesthesia consent with the goal of increasing the parents' understanding of the plan, risks, and benefits associated with administering sedation and anesthesia to a child (Gentry et al., 2015).

Firdouse et al. (2017) concluded that a checklist can be beneficial in gaining consent from parents. This enables the provider to include all key elements when obtaining consent. Although the checklist made the process more reliable, it did not aid in improving the parent's level of comfort with the procedure itself. These researchers recommended that future research investigations concentrate on the pediatric surrogate decision maker. This research should also include investigating anxiety in the pediatric surrogate who is responsible for giving consent.

Safety and Outpatient Pediatric Sedation

Several studies (Antunes et al., 2016; Dag et al., 2014; Qiao et al., 2017) report using varying types of anesthesia agents for sedating pediatric patients. Attri et al. (2017) and Qiao et al. (2017) studied the effects of different combinations of sedation medications on patients. Ketamine is a dissociative drug that has minimal effects on the cardiovascular system. Because of its properties of hemodynamic stability, it is frequently used for sedation in the pediatric population (Attri et al., 2017). Attri et al. (2017) and Qiao et al. (2017) found that ketamine significantly increased respiratory secretions, which are frequently associated with the risk of laryngospasm. According to

Spera et al. (2017), any type of secretion can cause a laryngospasm. Secretions such as saliva, blood, and irrigating fluids can cause laryngospasm in a patient who is not intubated for the anesthetic (Spera et al., 2017). Attri et al. (2017) recommended using an antisialogog to decrease salivary secretions.

von Ungern-Sternberg, Ramgolam, Hall Sly, and Habre (2015) concluded that a thorough pre-anesthetic evaluation enables providers to identify children at a higher risk for a respiratory critical event. In the study by von Ungern-Sterberg et al. (2015), blood was drawn in pediatric patients after induction of anesthesia. This blood was tested for common allergic markers associated with a reactive, irritable airway. There were no significant differences between pediatric patients with a higher level of allergic markers and patients with normal levels associated with experiencing a respiratory event during anesthesia. Therefore, the researchers concluded that the clinician's assessment is superior to an immunological blood test in determining a child at risk for a respiratory incident (von Ungern-Sterberg et al., 2015).

Critical Events and Simulation Training in the Perioperative Area

Critical events can be defined as incidents that potentially put a patient at risk for an adverse event (Cronje, 2015). Quickly identifying and treating the patient when a critical event occurs are key elements to an improved patient outcome (Cronje, 2015). Moreover, studies support that reporting, analyzing, and debriefing critical events increase patient safety related to preventing harm and thus improve patient outcome (Dias, Dave, Chiluveru, & Garasia, 2016; Lee et al., 2016). These critical events are rare but can be life-threatening. Simulation training is an effective method for increasing the

competencies of providers to react appropriately to a critical event (Hegland, Aarlie, Stremme, & Jamtvedt, 2017; Kato & Kataoka, 2017).

Everett et al. (2013) and Kato and Kataoka (2017) reported an increase in both knowledge and performance ability in participants with the utilization of simulation training evaluation sessions. Everett et al. (2017) also compared different methods of simulation evaluations that would aid in determining a provider's readiness to perform during actual critical events. The researchers concluded that a global rating system used during the simulation was a more reliable tool than checklists. According to the Dental Board of California (2016), critical event simulation training is useful in educating staff for unanticipated events. Some examples of critical event training identified by the Dental Board as important are airway fire, allergic reaction, aspiration, laryngospasm, bronchospasm, and negative pressure pulmonary edema (The Dental Board of California, 2016).

Triage

When a critical event occurs, the provider has a responsibility to respond appropriately and quickly to the incident. A perioperative flowchart can aid a practitioner during critical events for decision making, including the possibility of transporting the patient to a more appropriate higher level of care facility. Aspiration, hypoxia, and anaphylaxis are some examples of critical pediatric events that could necessitate a transfer of care from an ambulatory surgical center to a hospital for follow-up and treatment. Although these events have a low occurrence rate, they are associated with an increase in morbidity and mortality (Walker, 2013). The standard of care for aspiration is intubation, high levels of oxygen, antibiotics and a chest X-ray (Walker, 2013). Due to

the limited availability of these resources in an outpatient surgery center to deliver this higher level of care, the patient requires an immediate transfer of care to a setting with a higher level of clinical expertise onsite. Although the literature differs in the incidence of aspiration, the treatment remains the same as outlined by Walker (2013).

Lucy, Gandhi, Gross, and McNair (2017) published a study on pediatric hospital admissions after dental surgery and concluded that the highest incidence of pediatric admission post dental anesthesia was anesthesia induced intractable emesis after awakening and hypoxia related to laryngospasm or bronchospasm. In an ambulatory surgery center, these critical conditions would require a transfer of care for admission to a higher level of care. The AAP's (2019) policy statement on monitoring and management of pediatric patients before, during, and after sedation for diagnostic and therapeutic procedures supports the use of guidelines to aid ambulatory healthcare facilities in promoting a safe environment for a pediatric patient requiring an anesthetic. The AAP policy states it is important to have an agreement between facilities should a child require transferring to a facility with a higher level of care due to a critical incidence that requires additional treatment.

Quality Management

Bajwa and Jinal (2014) define quality management as the measurement and monitoring of patient outcomes. Elements of the quality management process of anesthesia identified by the researchers are the preoperative assessment, methods for QI, and the reporting of incidents or near misses (Bajwa & Jinal, 2014). Some quality management tools are instruments that identify common goals, provide daily guidelines, develop checklists, and organize debriefings (Bajwa et al. 2014; Oak et al., 2015).

Oak et al. (2015) specifically identified checklists in pediatric surgery as a quality management tool. The results showed that checklists are effective in increasing communication as well as identifying near misses. Near misses were defined as events that caused or could have caused a catastrophic event. These events included identification name tags on patients' arms which had fallen off, incorrect and incomplete consent forms, and missing antibiotic orders (Oak et al., 2015). Firdouse et al. (2017) and Oak et al. (2015) concluded that the standardization of checklists can facilitate the critical components of the surgical procedure process.

Root Cause Analysis

Root cause analysis is a system in which risk is assessed and evaluated (National Patient Safety Foundation, 2016). The purpose of risk management is to identify risks and potential events that can cause harm to patients. Identifying the root cause of an event enables an organization to put systems in place to prevent harm. The system of preventing harm by constructing safety frameworks to build on is the ultimate benefit emerging out of a root cause analysis (National Patient Safety Foundation, 2016). It is important for the investigators of the root cause to communicate with the team or individual who identified an event to be investigated. Debriefing enables administrators to communicate their commitment to patient safety and improved patient outcome. This level of communication increases the providers trust in the organization itself (National Patient Safety Foundation, 2016).

Debriefing

Debriefing is defined by Cho (2014) as the conversation that happens after a critical event occurs. This is a sharing of emotions, information, and experiences (Cho,

2014). Debriefing an anesthetic event increases patient safety and decreases the possibility of the event occurring again. Recognizing and reporting critical events as they occur are important factors for improving patient safety and outcome (Magill et al., 2017). Magill et al. (2017) recognized there was also improvement in the team members' perceptions of safety culture within their department. Magill and colleagues reported that the debriefing process after a critical event is significant for identifying important safety and patient outcome issues. Finally, it was also reported that administrative support of debriefing aided in improved communication within the team. This increased communication had a significant effect on patient safety.

Pimental, Choi, Fiumara, Kachalia, and Urman (2017) found varying degrees of a safety culture within the perioperative area. Interestingly, the highest perceptions of safety were reported as intradepartmental, and the lowest perception of safety was noted as occurring between hospital units. The researchers concluded the need for increased communication between units. Evidence from the analysis suggested that the nonpunitive actions of management when an error occurs are associated with a higher rate of reporting near misses or errors in clinical practice by providers (Pimental et al., 2017).

Debriefing is a process of supporting the teams' emotional experience after a critical event. The goal of debriefing is to decrease the teams' stress and increase the perception of support by peers and superiors (Gunasingam, Burns, Edwards, Dinh, & Walton, 2015). In a randomized control study, Gunsingam et al. (2015) reported that postgraduate physicians believed the debriefing process was valuable; however, the researchers concluded it was not significant in preventing burnout. Gunsingam et al.

(2015) defined burnout as a decrease of personal accomplishments, an increase of emotional desperation, and an increase of withdrawal from the people around them. In conclusion, the researchers suggested further research should be done on a larger scale to achieve a better understanding of the benefit of debriefing to prevent stress and burnout.

Arriaga et al. (2019) and Gunasingam et al. (2015) support the concept of debriefing and applying this strategy to increase emotional wellness in providers after stressful events. Arriaga et al. (2019) noted that poor communication skills between team members decreased the incidence of debriefing. This was caused by nonparticipation in the debriefing session due to the team members' unwillingness to engage in conversation. When a debriefing is not conducted immediately after an event, a subsequent debriefing session can still take place.

Some members of the team might require an opportunity to process the event. Arriaga et al. (2019) identified this type of later debriefing as a cold debrief and furthermore stated that, although organizations have deemed the cold debrief as valuable to the team, it should not be the normal process of debriefing. Debriefing is also utilized to identify gaps in knowledge. Arriaga et al. (2019) identified hot debriefing as occurring within 48 hours of the event. This allows the team to immediately address the issues. These conversations can lead to the acknowledgment of learning opportunities. These learning opportunities can decrease the risk of the event happening again (Arriaga et al., 2019).

Just Culture

Just culture can be defined as an environment that is created to allow providers to openly report errors, near misses and patient safety concern without the fear of retributive

punishment (Dekker & Breakey. 2016). The three elements just culture distinguishes between are human error, at-risk behavior, and the act of recklessness (Dekker, 2016; Dekker & Breakey, 2016). McCall and Pruchnicki (2017) illustrate how industries involved in high consequence outcomes require a just culture milieu which consists of balancing self-reporting and accountability. McCall and Pruchnicki (2017) and Dekker (2016) identify that blame-free is not the same as lack of accountability. When accountability is encouraged in a positive manner, the practitioner is allowed to be intimately involved with creating a safe environment (Dekker, 2016).

Conclusion

The evidence included in this literature review supports the formalized development and implementation of standardized guidelines as a credible method for reducing morbidity and mortality associated with anesthesia in the outpatient pediatric dental setting. A formal systematic method for managing the pediatric patient in an outpatient dental surgery center improves patient outcomes. An anesthesia tool kit is necessary to decrease mortality and morbidity in this vulnerable population. The literature emphasized the development of guidelines to include a pre-anesthetic checklist for assessment and consent, critical events training, a quality management tool, and triage planning post-critical event.

METHODS

The aim of this DNP project was to develop and evaluate guidelines for an anesthesia practice in the pediatric dental outpatient setting that were agreed upon by an expert panel. Clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) were developed and evaluated based on the improvement model utilizing the PDSA framework (Langley et al., 2009). The utilization of the PDSA cycle was appropriate for developing these guidelines. The project was divided into two phases. The first phase included the *Plan* step of the PDSA cycle; this was completed during the doctoral project. The evaluation of the guidelines during phase one was accomplished by a Delphi panel of experts. The second phase of *Do-Study-Act* will be conducted post-doctorate completion.

Setting

Clinical practice guidelines were developed for an ambulatory surgery center in the city of Indio, which is located 23 miles east of Palm Springs and 127 miles east of Los Angeles, California. The population of Indio in 2010 was 76,036. Children under the age of 18 account for 27% of the population. Demographics of the city are 68% Hispanic, 26% Caucasian, 3% Black, and 3% Asian. The average income of the population is \$49,555. The pediatric dental surgery center is Joint Commission approved and MediCal certified. The center's service area encompasses Riverside, San Bernardino, and Imperial Counties. The anesthesia department consists of physician anesthesiologists, certified nurse anesthetists, and dental anesthesiologists. The perioperative team consists of two registered nurses, two to three pediatric dentists, two recovery nurses, and four dental assistants.

Ethical Issues

The project was approved through the institutional review board (IRB) at California State University Long Beach (Appendix D). A letter of approval was obtained by the author from the board of directors at the Indio Surgery Center (Appendix E). This project was the development and evaluation of guidelines for a pediatric dental outpatient surgery center. The evaluation did not directly involve human subjects. The Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guideline (PDAG) evaluation process was conducted using the Delphi Method (Appendix F).

Guideline Project Design-PDSA Framework Model

Planning for this project included identifying the process, outcome, and balancing measures for developing CPGs. The planning phase included organizing a team of stakeholders from the surgery center. The team included two CRNAs, a dental anesthesiologist, the director of the surgery center, two registered nurses, a dental assistant and a pediatric dentist. Staff meetings were held to introduce the project, discuss the development of CPGs, and discuss the evaluation of the guidelines with the anticipation of gaining input and support for the application of the guidelines.

Guidelines include (a) pre-operative instructions and education forms, (b) a standardized anesthesia assessment protocol including a detailed consent form, (c) critical event training for outpatient surgery center staff, (d) development and evaluation of a triage plan for appropriate transfer to a higher level of care, and (e) development of a QI tool to capture anesthesia events used for outcome improvement.

Plan

1. Conduct a ROL and determine the levels of evidence for the literature. (3 weeks).
2. Gain approval from the IRB committee at California State University, Long Beach (3 weeks.)
3. Identify the team members for the project (1 week).
4. Identify the qualifications needed for the expert panel to evaluate the guidelines (1 week).
5. Contact potential members for the expert panel and finalize the panel (1 week).
6. Plan a meeting for the team members and begin establishing process, outcome, and balancing measures for the different aspects of the guidelines. These to include pre-anesthesia consent and education, simulation training, QI tool, and triage planning (2 weeks).
7. Oversee team development of an initial draft of the guidelines (2 weeks).
8. Communicate with the expert panel and send the guideline draft to the panel (1 week).
9. Meet with team members regarding comments obtained from the panel (1 week).
10. Integrate feedback into new guideline development (3 days).
11. Send final guideline proposal to the panel and obtain feedback (2 weeks).

Do

1. Establish organizational approval of guidelines (1 week).
2. Implement guidelines (4 weeks).
3. Collect process, outcome data, and balancing data (4 weeks).

Study

1. Study data collection (2 weeks)
2. Communicate with the panel of experts on the results of data (1 week).
3. Revise the guidelines as appropriate (1 week).

Act

1. Written guidelines approved by expert panel. (4 weeks).
2. Final guidelines dissemination at conference (4 weeks).
3. Continue to communicate with the expert panel on a quarterly basis and revise as appropriate.

Preoperative Consent and Assessment

Based on the ROL, standardized checklists can lead to a reliable process for the consenting of patients as well as assessing patients for the appropriateness of receiving anesthesia at an ambulatory surgery center. The checklists developed for this project were formulated based on evidenced-based research that were included in the literature review. It is proposed that the anesthesia providers will call the patient's guardian before the day of surgery and follow the standardized checklist. This checklist includes education regarding preoperative instructions. On the day of surgery, the consent for the anesthetic is obtained by the provider scheduled to administer the anesthetic who will follow the same checklist utilized prior to surgery to assure accuracy and completeness and parental understanding.

Critical Event Training

Critical events training (CET) for the dental surgery center staff focuses on three topics. The CET includes airway emergencies, aspiration, and anaphylaxis. Based on the review of literature, simulated training should include the key elements associated with

anesthesia critical events. The anesthesia simulation educator coordinates with the director of the surgery center and determines a four-hour window for the training day utilizing a lesson plan (Appendix G). During the first 30 minutes of the training session, the staff complete a pretest. This serves as the baseline evaluation of the three simulation scenarios. The anesthesia educator provides education and instruction regarding each of the three scenarios. A simulated event then begins. During the simulation questions and just culture behavior is encouraged. A debriefing is performed after each simulation for educational purposes and to provide an opportunity for staff to have a time of reflection and decompression of stressors. After the three scenarios are completed CRNA educators administer a post-test. The post-test is similar to but not an exact copy of the pretest. Both tests were developed using EBP guidelines for testing knowledge in simulation training.

Triage to Higher Level of Care

Transporting children to a higher level of care can be challenging and complicated. Developing appropriate triage pathways requires an in-depth analysis of which events warrant a transfer to a medical center that can provide the necessary level of care. Educating staff about the services provided at different specialty hospitals and defining a clear transfer process will be included in the transport pathway of the clinical practice guideline. John F. Kennedy Medical Center is five miles east of the surgery center and is an acute care facility. Loma Linda Children's Hospital is 70 miles east of the surgery center and has a pediatric intensive care unit. A system for transporting children to these centers was formalized and included in the PDAG.

Quality Improvement Checklist of Unanticipated Events

The QI Checklist included in the guidelines was developed based on the evidence reported in this project. The tool was developed and evaluated by the project team and the expert panel. Based on the responses of the team and expert panel, the tool was revised and included in the guidelines.

Evaluation

The evaluation of the guidelines was conducted using the Delphi Method. The Delphi Method involved identifying a panel of seven experts who participated in a series of several rounds of discussion and evaluation until consensus was reached. The expert panel consisted of two physician anesthesiologists, a dental anesthesiologist, two certified nurse anesthetists familiar with pediatric dental outpatient anesthesia, and two advanced practice registered nurses who also practice at a dental outpatient center. These experts were recruited using email communication, and all panel members were currently involved in the specialty of pediatric dental procedures. Two of the initial panel members have published scholarly work based on pediatric dental anesthesia. Panel members were recruited from scholarly publications and professional organizations. This ensured a nonbiased panel with diverse opinions and increased the validity of the guidelines. Anonymity and feedback are key elements of the Delphi Method. To ensure anonymity, a Qualtrics survey was developed for the evaluation of the guidelines. Data collected in this process were shared with the panel through e-mailing, thus fulfilling the feedback element (Avella, 2016).

RESULTS

Planning for this project included identifying the process, outcome, and balancing measures for developing CPGs. The planning phase included organizing a team of stakeholders from the surgery center. The team included two CRNAs, a dental anesthesiologist, the director of the surgery center, two nurse practitioners, and a pediatric dentist. Staff meetings were held to introduce the project, discuss the development of CPGs, and discuss the evaluation of the guidelines with the anticipation of gaining input and support for the application of the guidelines.

Guidelines include (a) pre-operative instructions and education, (b) standardized anesthesia assessment protocol including a detailed consent form, (c) critical event training for outpatient surgery center staff, (d) development and evaluation of a triage plan for appropriate transfer to a higher level of care, and (e) development of a QI tool to capture anesthesia events used for outcome improvement.

The pediatric dental guidelines were developed by the stakeholders and then sent to two DNP educated CRNAs to review the articles that became the foundation for the recommendations identified in the various sections of the guidelines (Appendix H). These individuals were asked to rate the articles for reliability and validity based on the John Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice level quality guidelines (Appendix I). There was 100% agreement between the reviewers regarding the strength of the evidence and the significance of the results related to issues of validity and reliability of their finding. In addition, the two CRNA reviewers were asked to address the question of feasibility of implementing the guideline recommendations in ambulatory surgery centers. These reviewers were in 100% agreement that the guidelines were feasible in an outpatient

surgery setting for dental anesthesia. The guidelines were then reviewed for professional feedback by three medical anesthesiologists (one chief of anesthesia) and a CRNA, all of whom are on staff at the same medical center (separate from the ambulatory surgery center). These providers administer anesthesia to pediatric dental patients. The reviewers' comments were recorded and reviewed by the stakeholders at the pediatric dental outpatient center. The stakeholders then edited the guidelines based on the reviewers' feedback.

Qualtrics was utilized for the Delphi survey evaluation (Appendix J). This tool provides statistical analysis of participant responses and allows the panel members to remain anonymous. It is a tool that allows the researcher to collect feedback and data based on questions that the researcher creates. The survey design was developed by the primary author and then reviewed by the team leader and team member. When final approval of the survey tool was obtained, the first round of Delphi was conducted.

The Delphi panel members who participated in the first round of Delphi included two medical anesthesiologists, a dental anesthesiologist, a PhD prepared CRNA, a pediatric dental CRNA, and two nurse practitioners who practice at a dental surgery center. There was 75% consensus reached during the first round of Delphi. There was disagreement with the recommendation of critical events training for dental outpatient facilities. Two panel members were concerned with the frequency of the critical event training. One of the two panel members stated that conducting this type of training in a private dental office would not be financially feasible. The other panel member suggested this training occur every 3 months.

The stakeholders were consulted, and edits were initiated. During this time of evaluation one of the Delphi members reached out to the researcher and discussed dropping out of the Delphi panel due to the time it would take to participate on the panel and the in-depth evaluation of the guidelines. Through email communication the panelist supported the proposed guidelines but withdrew due to the panelist's other time commitments. This panelist's feedback was appreciated, and guidelines were altered to include the recommended changes. An alternate anesthesiologist was contacted and added to the Delphi panel.

The second Delphi round identified that there remained a question in regard to the critical event training. The second round Delphi achieved a 90% consensus. Disagreement was noted again in the critical events training section of the guidelines. Stakeholders were again consulted, and the third round Delphi survey was developed with a two-question survey to elicit more information regarding the topic of disagreement.

The third round Delphi was completed with complete consensus and the final pediatric dental guidelines were presented to the stakeholders at the surgery center. The primary researcher disseminated the pediatric dental anesthesia guidelines at the California Association of Nurse Anesthetist meeting in October 2019.

Discussion

The purposed DNP project was to develop and evaluate CPGs for a pediatric dental anesthesia ambulatory surgery center. The PDSA model was used as the framework to conduct this work. The PDSA model will be utilized to begin the second phase of implementation of the guidelines post-doctorate.

Evidence-based research supports improvement in clinical practice with the use of safety guidelines when administering anesthesia to pediatric patients (AAP, 2016). These written standardized guidelines used in a practice setting are necessary to provide quality care to this vulnerable population.

Guideline Recommendations

In order to meet all the key elements of consent (Appendix K-L) it recommended that an anesthesia assessment interview be conducted by an anesthesia provider or a staff member trained in phone assessments and pre-anesthesia education (Appendix M). Findings from this assessment should then be recorded on a standardized pre-anesthesia assessment checklist. Utilizing the same but labeled procedural assessment checklist, the anesthesia provider should conduct and record an anesthesia assessment on the day of the procedure for completeness and accuracy. This guideline was based on the research of Firdouse, Ascender, Koyle, & Fecteau (2017) and Oak et al. (2015).

It is recommended that a quality management (QM) checklist for QI should be used for root cause analysis of unanticipated events (Appendix N). Debriefing after all critical events with the use of just culture to assure all members of the team will be heard and concerns addressed. All near misses should be tracked and analyzed for quality care improvement (Firdouse et al., 2017; Magill et al., 2017; National Patient Safety Foundation 2016).

To increase the staff's ability to react appropriately to a critical event, simulation training should be conducted on a routine basis and recorded for future new staff orientation. This training should be available to all new staff during their orientation phase of employment and conducted by a qualified anesthesia provider as supported by

studies conducted by Arriaga et al. (2019), Dekker, (2016), Dekker and Breake (2016), McCall and Pruchnicki (2017), and Watkins et al. (2016) (Appendix O-Q).

Due to the limited resources available in outpatient procedural areas, triaging to a higher level of care is recommended for the following situations: malignant hyperthermia, hypoxia airway fire, anaphylaxis, suspected pulmonary edema, suspected aspiration, and patients receiving racemic-epinephrine after 3 hours of required observation who continue to have an oxygen saturation below 98% (Appendix R). Unstable patients should be transferred to a level one pediatric trauma center and stable patients transferred to the closest emergency department by an emergency medical system. Establishing relationships with local hospitals and appropriate local trauma centers is recommended (Farrohknia et al., 2011).

Clinical Implications for the PDAG

Dissemination of the PDAGs has occurred at the primary researcher's state professional organization. Anesthesia providers within the state have contacted the researcher regarding the implementation of the guidelines. The second phase continued utilizing the PDSA model for implementation and dissemination of the PDSA guidelines. The implementation of the project began at the Indio Surgery Center in April of 2020. Stakeholders input is utilized, and data collection is ongoing for the purpose of guideline revision. Further dissemination of the guidelines will occur at the 2020 California Dental Association conference. The author will be assisting the California Association of Nurse Anesthetists in manning an exhibition booth to promote and disseminate the PDAGs. Dissemination of the PDAGs will include the importance of adherence to guidelines. Encouraging the culture of guideline adherence for the purpose of decreasing morbidity

and mortality in this population will be emphasized in the dissemination process (Hassan, 2017).

Future Recommendations

Currently there is limited research on CPGs and dental anesthesia, specifically in the pediatric population. Reliable and valid research needs to be conducted in this patient population to improve patient outcome. The PDSA model fits well into the concept of a living document to prevent the guidelines from becoming outdated (Hassan, 2017).

It is proposed post-doctorate that the anesthesia providers or trained staff at the Indio pediatric dental center will call the patient's guardian before the day of surgery and the standardized checklist will be followed. Pre-procedural education will be conducted by an anesthesia provider or staff member at this time. When a staff member other than an anesthesia provider conducts this interview and completes the checklist, this staff member will be trained by the anesthesia provider. To assure competency, an anesthesia provider will monitor the staff member interviews. The staff member will be deemed qualified after a demonstration of three accurate and complete assessments and patient education are witnessed.

On the day of surgery, the anesthesia provider scheduled to administer the anesthetic will obtain the consent for anesthesia and conduct an anesthesia assessment by repeating the anesthesia assessment checklist. This will be utilized to assure accuracy, completeness, and parental understanding. Beginning April 2020, the implementation sample size for this second phase evaluation will be 100 patients. The pre-procedure checklist data collected in phase two will be compared to data collected on the subsequent day of the dental procedure to ascertain the percentage of accuracy of

information. The expected outcome is a 90% agreement between the two forms. It is estimated that it will take until July 2020 to obtain the 100 patients for comparison.

The first CET will take place and recorded in April 2020. The staff training will consist 3 dental assistants, 6 registered nurses, 2 dentists and 4 anesthesia providers. A post-test will be conducted with an improvement score goal of 100% accuracy for all staff members.

The QI checklist will be implemented in April 2020. A sample size of 100 charts will be audited by the peer review method. When a chart is shown to have a quality improvement issue, the auditor will investigate whether a quality improvement checklist has been completed. By July 2020, 100% of the charts will have a QI checklist completed by a staff member or provider.

In April 2020 the triage pathways will be posted in the three operating room suites in the Indio Surgery Center. The education of all staff members will be recorded and completed in April 2020. The triage information and locations will be posted in the preoperative and postoperative areas at this time.

The goal of utilizing the PDAGs locally, state-wide, and nationally is to serve to improve the morbidity and mortality in this vulnerable population of pediatric patients. No child should suffer a serious outcome or at its worse mortality because of human failure to identify and react to an anesthetic complication. It is a provider's duty to serve and protect.

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APPENDIX A

PEDIATRIC DENTAL ANESTHESIA GUIDELINES

Introduction

Standardized pediatric dental guidelines provide a written criterion for patient care. Although anesthesia complications in this population of children are rare, continued efforts to improve care is important. Evidence-based research supports improvement in clinical practice with the use of safety guidelines when administering anesthesia to pediatric patients (AAP, 2016). These written standardized guidelines used in a practice setting are necessary to provide quality care to this vulnerable population.

Background

In school-age children, poor dentition has been linked to below average academic performance, maladjusted psychosocial behavior, and overall decreased physical health (Guarnizo-Herreno & Wehby, 2012; level of evidence III, Quality B). Dental caries are five times more likely to occur in children ages 5 to 17 than a diagnosis of asthma (Sen et al., 2013; Level of evidence III, Quality A). Achembong, Kranz, and Rozier (2014)

noted in their national-based ecologic study that untreated caries was ranked tenth out of 295 diseases and injuries afflicting children. Furthermore, untreated dental disease can lead to decreased quality of life for children with this issue (Achembong et al., 2014; Level of evidence III Quality B).

From January 1, 2010, to December 31, 2015, the Dental Board of California reported nine pediatric deaths associated with dental procedures. In the same six-year period, the board was notified of 45 hospitalizations. Due to the absence of a national reporting database for anesthesia-related morbidity and mortality in private dental offices and outpatient and inpatient settings, it is difficult to monitor untoward outcomes unless they are reported to the individual state boards based on state regulations (The Dental Board of California, 2016; Level of evidence IV, Quality A).

Patient safety and the administration of anesthesia with cautious oversight among this population can be challenging. Anesthesia complications in outpatient facilities are rare but do occur. Aspiration, airway fire, and anaphylaxis are some of these rare events (Cote & Wilson, 2016; Level of evidence IV, Quality A). These rare events can occur during sedation, as in the Cote and Wilson research suggests, as well as during the administration of moderate sedation and general anesthesia cases as well. The most common complication associated with children under the influence of sedation and general anesthesia is respiratory compromise (Spera et al., 2017; Level of evidence III, Quality B). However, when guidelines are in place and followed, anesthesia risks are minimized (American Association of Nurse Anesthetists, 2017).

The failure to recognize at-risk patient situations or unforeseen events can lead to catastrophic events if not treated early and appropriately. In outpatient facilities, an

ineffective resuscitative measure or an inappropriate intervention is the primary reason for an adverse outcome (Cote & Wilson, 2016; Level of evidence IV, Quality A). The utilization of evidence-based practice guidelines and best practice standards of care can reduce mortality and morbidity in pediatric dental patients receiving anesthesia (Dental Board of California, 2016; Level of evidence IV, Quality A).

Evidence-Based Practice

Guideline Statement

Evidence supports the formalized development and implementation of standardized guidelines as a credible method for reducing mortality and morbidity associated with anesthesia in the outpatient setting. Studies rated as Level of evidence III-V and Quality A & B support the recommendation for the development of this Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guideline.

A formal systematic method for managing the pediatric patient in an outpatient dental surgery center improves patient outcomes. Implementation of pediatric dental anesthesia guidelines is an essential quality measure for dental centers caring for pediatric patients to decrease mortality and morbidity in this vulnerable population. The guidelines include pre-anesthesia assessment checklist (See pediatric dental pre-anesthesia assessment form), consent form (See anesthesia consent form), pre-procedural anesthesia education (See pre-procedural patient education for anesthesia form), quality management checklist (See quality management checklist of unanticipated events), critical event training lesson plan (See critical event training lesson plan), and critical event triage pathways (See critical event triage pathways).

Evidence-based practice is based on research studies that are categorized into different grades of evidence. The Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice clinical-decision making evidence tool (Johns Hopkins Center for Evidence-Based Practice, 2017) (Level of evidence IV, Quality A) was used for evidence grading of research studies and other manuscripts utilized in this review of the literature (ROL) conducted in developing this guideline (See Johns Hopkins Center for Evidence-Based Practice chart). These tools are used to evaluate research studies by addressing the strength of evidence and the significance of the study results for clinical practice. The JHNEBP grading system ranges from a 1-5 (level of evidence) and from A through C (quality of the evidence in ranking). Grades 1 and A represent the highest evidence level and quality of studies, which include randomized control trials and meta-analysis reviews (Bootland, Coughlan, Galloway, Goubet, & McWhirter, 2017).

The ROL analyzed for this guideline represents a limited number of studies related to safety and pediatric dental anesthesia and also revealed a gap in the literature for unbiased, high-level systematic reviews and meta-analyses on these same topics. The majority of studies cited in this practice guideline were Grade 1- 3 based on the JHNEBP criteria.

Assessment, Consent and Parental Information Checklists

Guideline Statement

An anesthesia assessment interview should be conducted by an anesthesia provider or a staff member trained in phone assessments and pre-anesthesia education.

Findings from this assessment are recorded on a standardized pre-anesthesia

assessment checklist. Utilizing the same but labeled procedural assessment checklist, the anesthesia provider will conduct and record an anesthesia assessment on the day of the procedure for completeness and accuracy. Recommendation for this guideline statement are based on the Level of Evidence III and Quality B.

Based on the ROL, standardized checklists can lead to a reliable process for the consenting of patients as well as assessing the patients for the appropriateness of receiving anesthesia at an ambulatory surgery center (Firdouse, Ascender, Koyle, & Fecteau, 2017; Level of evidence III, Quality B). The checklists developed for this project were formulated based on the findings from empirical research studies that were included in the literature review (See anesthesia informed consent checklist for pediatric dental patients). Oak et al. (2015) (Level of evidence III, Quality B), specifically identified checklists in pediatric surgery as a quality management tool. The results showed that checklists are effective both in increasing communication and identifying near misses. It is proposed that the anesthesia providers or trained staff will call the patient's guardian before the day of surgery and the standardized checklist will be followed. Pre-procedural education will be conducted by this provider or staff member at this time. When a staff member other than an anesthesia provider conducts this interview and completes the checklist, this staff member will be trained by the anesthesia provider. To assure competency, an anesthesia provider will monitor the staff member interviews. The staff member will be deemed qualified after a demonstration of three accurate and complete assessments and patient education are witnessed.

On the day of surgery, the anesthesia provider scheduled to administer the anesthetic will obtain the consent for anesthesia and conduct an anesthesia assessment by repeating the

anesthesia assessment checklist. This will be utilized to assure accuracy, completeness and parental understanding.

Critical Event Training and Curriculum

Guideline Statement

To increase the staff's ability to react appropriately to a critical event, simulation training should be conducted on a routine basis and recorded for future new staff orientation. This training should be available to all new staff during their orientation phase of employment and conducted by a qualified anesthesia provider. Recommendation for this guideline statement are based on Level of Evidence III-V and Quality A.

Critical event training for the dental surgery center staff includes simulation training for the management of three scenarios of relevance to the pediatric dental patient: common airway complications (laryngospasm, bronchospasm, airway obstruction) aspiration, and anaphylaxis. This skills training will be scheduled for staff on a routine basis deemed necessary and feasible for administration and anesthesia. A pretest will be administered by the anesthesia educator to collect critical event baseline data on staff knowledge regarding airway fires, anaphylaxis and aspiration (See pre-test critical events testing for dental assistants and registered nurses form).

Each of the three critical events scenarios provides education, instruction, and skill testing (Watkins et. al, 2016; Level of evidence III, Quality B). During the training sessions the anesthesia provider will encourage questioning by participants and just

culture behavior. Just culture can be defined as an environment that is created to allow providers to openly report errors, near misses and patient safety concern without the fear of retributive punishment (Dekker & Breakey. 2016) (Level of evidence V, Quality A). McCall and Pruchnicki (2017) (Level of evidence V, Quality A) illustrate how industries involved in high consequence outcomes require a just culture milieu which consists of balancing self-reporting and accountability. McCall and Pruchnicki (2017) and Dekker (2016) (Level of evidence V, Quality A) identify that blame-free is not the same as lack of accountability. When accountability is encouraged in a positive manner the practitioner is allowed to be intimately involved with creating a safe environment (Dekker, 2016).

The anesthesia trainer will debrief the participants after each simulation for educational purposes as well as to provide an opportunity for staff to have time for reflection and decompression of stressors (Arriaga et. al, 2019; Level of evidence III, Quality A). After completion of the three scenarios the educators will administer a post-test (See post-test for critical event training form). The post-test is similar to but is not an exact copy of the pretest. An evaluation of the critical event training will be provided for staff feedback (See critical event simulation evaluation form).

Triage to Higher Level of Care

Guideline Statement

Due to the limited resources available in outpatient procedural areas, triaging to a higher level of care is recommended for the following situations: malignant hyperthermia, hypoxia airway fire, anaphylaxis, suspected pulmonary edema, suspected aspiration, and patients receiving racemic-epinephrine after 3 hours of

required observation who continue to have an oxygen saturation below 98%, Unstable patients should be transferred to a level one pediatric trauma center and stable patients transferred to the closest emergency department by an emergency medical system. Establishing relationships with local hospitals and appropriate local trauma centers is recommended. Recommendation is based on Level of evidence I and Quality A.

Transporting children to a higher level of care can be challenging and complicated. Developing appropriate triage pathways requires an in-depth analysis of which events warrant a transfer to which level of medical center. Educating staff about medical services provided at the different specialty hospitals and defining a standardized process that includes policies and procedures is included in the transport pathways of the clinical practice guidelines (See triage pathways).

Farrohknia et al., (2011) reported in a systematic review for triage emergency rooms that a triage system is a component of assessing patient care urgency. These checklists aid providers in obtaining the goal of decreasing mortality and morbidity. Few quality triage assessment checklists have been developed and supported by evidence-based practice (Farrohknia et al., 2011).

Pediatric Dental Anesthesia: Quality Management Checklist

Guideline statement

A quality management (QM) checklist for quality improvement (QI) will be used for root cause analysis of unanticipated events. Debriefing after all critical events with

the use of just culture to assure all members of the team will be heard and concerns addressed. All near misses will be tracked and analyzed for quality care improvement. Recommendation is based on the Level of evidence III -IV and Quality A.

Quality improvement is a process of improving patient care through altering the current system. Root cause analysis is a process by which risk is assessed and evaluated (National Patient Safety Foundation, 2016; Level of evidence IV, Quality A). The purpose of risk management is to identify risks and potential events that can cause harm to patients. Identifying the root cause of an event enables an organization to put systems in place to prevent harm. The system of preventing harm by constructing safety frameworks to build on is the ultimate benefit emerging out of a root cause analysis (National Patient Safety Foundation, 2016). It is important for the investigators of the root cause to communicate with the team or individual who identified an event to be investigated. Debriefing enables administrators to communicate their commitment to patient safety and improved patient outcome. This level of communication increases the providers trust in the organization itself (National Patient Safety Foundation, 2016). The Quality Management Checklist has been developed based on the evidence and underwent review for validity and reliability utilizing a testing team of two DNP prepared CRNAs and an expert panel. The guideline checklist for QM focuses on and provides a tool to report critical events as they occur. This has been shown as important factors for improving patient outcome (Magill et al., 2017; Level of evidence IV, Quality B). The debriefing process after a critical event is significant for identifying important safety and patient outcome issues. Administrative support of debriefing also improves

communication within the team, which significantly impacts patient safety (Magill et al., 2017; Level of evidence IV, Quality B).

Near misses are defined as events that cause or could have caused a catastrophic event. These events included identification name tags on patients' arms which had fallen off, incorrect and incomplete consent forms, and missing antibiotic orders (Oak et al., 2015; Level of evidence III, Quality B. Firdouse et al. (2017) (Level of evidence III, Quality B) and Oak et al. (2015) (Level of evidence III, Quality B) concluded that the standardization of checklists can facilitate the critical components of the surgical procedure process. These elements of the QI checklist focus on these identified important events.

PEDIATRIC DENTAL PRE-ANESTHESIA ASSESSMENT

MEDICAL PROBLEMS	COMMENTS		
ALLERGIES	YES	NO	
HEART PROBLEMS	YES	NO	IF YES, NEEDS CONSULTATION AND CLEARANCE
ASTHMA- LAST ATTACK	YES WHEN	NO	
URGENT CARE EMERGENCY ROOM VISIT	YES WHEN	NO	
COLD IN THE LAST TWO WEEKS	YES WHEN WAS THE LAST DAY OF S/S	NO	
DIABETES TYPE I TYPE II	YES	NO	IF YES, NEEDS CONSULTATION AND CLEARANCE INSTRUCTIONS FROM ENDOCRINOLOGIST DIET CONTROLLED INSULIN DEPENDENT ORAL MEDICATION DOSAGE AND TIME OF MEDICATION
THYROID	YES	NO	
BLEEDING DISORDER	YES	NO	IF YES, NEEDS CONSULTATION AND CLEARANCE H&H NOTED WITH PROVIDER CLEARANCE
ANEMIC	YES		

DISABILITIES	YES TYPE	NO	
KIDNEY	YES	NO	
DAILY MEDICATIONS (Name, Amount, When)			
MEDICATION ORDERED BY A PROVIDER OR OVER THE COUNTER (Name, Amount, When)		NO	
SEEN BY A PROVIDER FOR ANY REASON OTHER THAN WELL CHECK UPS	YES REASON	NO	
SNORES	YES	NO	IF YES, NEEDS CONSULTATION AND CLEARANCE
ANESTHESIA HISTORY COMPLICATIONS	YES-TYPE TYPE	NO	IF YES, NEEDS CONSULTATION AND CLEARANCE
FAMILY HISTORY OF COMPLICATIONS FROM ANESTHESIA	YES TYPE	NO	IF YES, NEEDS CONSULTATION AND CLEARANCE
NPO STATUS	TIME		
HOSPITALIZATION OVER NIGHT	YES REASON	NO	
BMI IN THE 85 th PERCENTILE TO LESS THAN THE 95 TH PERCENTILE (CONSIDERED OVER WEIGHT)	YES	NO	IF YES, NEEDS CONSULTATION AND CLEARANCE
EQUAL TO OR GREATER THAN THE 95 TH PERCENTILE (CONSIDERED OBESE)	YES	NO	

ANESTHESIA CONSENT

Patient Name: _____

Date of Service: _____

Anesthesia Provider: _____

I understand that

_____ I will need anesthesia services for the dental procedure(s) to be done on the agreed date, and that the type of anesthesia to be used will depend upon the procedure and my physical condition.

_____ Anesthesia is a specialty which manages patients who are rendered unconscious or with diminished response to pain and stress during the dental procedure(s).

_____ During the course of the dental procedure, conditions may require additional or different anesthetic monitoring or techniques, and I consent to the anesthesia provider providing any additional necessary services for my benefit and well-being.

_____ No guarantees have been made by anyone regarding the anesthesia services which I am agreeing to have.

TYPE OF ANESTHESIA AND DEFINITIONS:

A. General Anesthesia

1. Total Intravenous Anesthesia: anesthetic medications are passed through an intravenous catheter into a vein.
2. Endotracheal Anesthesia: anesthetic and respiratory gases are passed through a tube placed in the trachea (windpipe via the nose or mouth).
3. Mask Induction Anesthesia: anesthesia gases are passed through a mask which covers the nose and mouth.

B. Nerve Blocks: dental blocks with anesthetic medications to be administered for post-procedural pain management

C. Monitored Anesthesia Care: includes the monitoring of at least blood pressure, oxygenation, respiration, heart-beat, and mental state, supplementing analgesia as needed.

Risks and Complications may include but not limited to: respiratory complications, intubation, longer stay at the surgery center, possible transfer to a higher level of care, allergic/adverse reaction, aspiration, pneumonia, seizures, brain damage, coma, dental injury, inability to reverse the effects of anesthesia, infection, localized swelling, pain, muscle aches, nausea, ophthalmic (eye) injury, positional nerve injury, recall of sound noise/ speech by others, sore throat and even death.

I have been fully advised and completely understand the alternatives to conscious sedation and general anesthesia. I accept the possible risks, side effects, complications and consequences of anesthesia. I acknowledge the receipt of the pre-operative instructions. It has been explained to me and I understand that there is no warranty and no guarantee as to any result or treatment. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about my child's anesthesia, and I am satisfied with the information provided to me. It is also understood that the anesthesia services are completely independent from the operating dentist's procedure.

I have read and understand the consent for anesthesia. I have had the opportunity to have all my questions answered regarding the risks, benefits and alternatives of anesthesia.

Patient Name _____ Date _____

Parent/Guardian's Name _____ Relationship _____

Food (time) _____ AM/PM Liquid (time) _____ AM/PM

Signature _____ Witness _____

PRE-PROCEDURAL PATIENT EDUCATION FOR ANESTHESIA

1. The child must have nothing to eat or drink for 8 hours prior to the arrival at the surgery center. The child must be supervised at all times 8 hours prior to the surgery to assure providers that the child has not had anything by mouth. The risk of aspiration is pneumonia. Aspiration can require antibiotics, hospitalization and even cause death.
2. Actively sick children presenting at the surgery center for surgery will be cancelled after assessment by team. This is due to the high risk of respiratory complications when children are sick, breathing treatments might be necessary. This type of respiratory complication may require a longer stay at the surgery center for the child to be observed and a delayed discharge home. There is always a possibility that when this occurs the child might need to be transferred and admitted to the nearest appropriate hospital for further treatment.
3. If the child snores while sleeping, there is a possibility that the child has enlarged tonsils. These enlarged tonsils can increase the risk of respiratory complications. These complications can result in, breathing treatments, a longer stay at the surgery center for observation, abandonment of the procedure and possible transfer to the nearest hospital for further treatment.
4. If the child wakes up ill or has been ill during the previous 2 weeks, please call the surgery center and inform the staff of the child's illness and reschedule as appropriate.
5. Patients with asthma and have been treated with steroids within the recent 6 months will have a steroid preparation given at the surgery center prior to the

administration of anesthesia. Please bring any and all medications the child is currently taking to the surgery center the day of surgery.

QUALITY IMPROVEMENT CHECKLIST OF UNANTICIPATED EVENTS

Unanticipated event	Circle possible reasons and actions
1. Difficult IV	Additional staff required Case cancelled and time of day noted
2. Incorrect Consent	Administration notified Parents notified
3. Unanticipated intubation in the OR	Reason for intubation and actions taken post intubation
4. PACU greater than 90 minutes	Anesthesia notified Racemic epinephrine given Additional medications given
5. Anesthesia provider intervention in PACU after sign off to PACU nurse	Action of the provider noted
6. Airway fire	Throat pack dry O2 at greater than 3 liters
7. Anaphylaxis reaction	All medication noted
8. Medication error or near miss	Look alike drugs Administration notified
9. Wrong X-rays on wrong patient	Multiple staff in room Notify administration
10. Nausea and vomiting greater than 30 minutes	Bleeding Patient dehydrated Antiemetics given Transferred to ED
11. Bleeding in PACU	Extractions without suturing History of bleeding disorders Surgeon notified Anesthesia notified
12. Day of surgery cancellation	Patient ill Heart murmur Parental decision NPO status Notify administration
13. Unplanned transfer to higher level facility	Aspiration Hypoxia Airway fire Bronchospasm Hospital transferred

PEDIATRIC DENTAL ANESTHESIA CRITICAL EVENT TRIAGE AND TRANSPORT PATHWAY

Critical events to be transferred to a higher level of care

- a. Hypoxia
- b. Airway Fire
- c. Anaphylaxis
- d. Malignant hyperthermia
- e. Suspected aspiration
- f. Patients receiving racemic epinephrine after 3 hours of required observation and still continues to have an Oxygen Saturation below 98%.
- g. Suspected pulmonary edema

Critical Events Procedural Checklist

1. Call for help by RN
2. All procedures in other OR suites are halted (when can safely be terminated) until the critical event has been appropriately managed. All available staff are to report to the to the area of the critical event.
3. Registered nurse manager or designee calls EMS for transport
4. Parental information given regarding care
5. Anesthesia provider to report to facility accepting patient
6. Anesthesia provider to go on transport with unstable patient

TRIAGE PATHWAY FOR AIRWAY FIRE

TRIAGE PATHWAY ASPIRATION**STABLE PATIENT**

INTUBATE

OUTPATIENT ADMINISTRATION NOTIFIES PARENT
REGARDING TRANSPORT TO NEAREST ED BY EMS

ADMINISTRATION NOTIFIES EMS OF TRANSPORT

IF O2 SATURATIONS CONSISTENTLY 100%
MAY EXTUBATE AND PREPARE PATIENT FOR
TRANSPORT TO NEAREST ED FOR CHEST XRAY

ANESTHESIA REPORTS TO ED ACCEPTING PROVIDER

TRIAGE TRANSPORT FOR ANAPHYLAXIS

INTUBATE

OUTPATIENT ADMINISTRATION CONTACTS EMS
NOTIFY PARENTS

TRANSPORT PATIENT TO NEAREST LEVEL ONE HOSPITAL
WITH EMS AND ANESTHESIA PROVIDER

TRIAGE PATHWAY FOR MALIGNANT HYPERTHERMIA

**TRIAGE PATHWAY FOR SUSTAINED HYPOXIA AND OR NEGATIVE
PRESSURE PULMONARY EDEMA**

CRITICAL EVENTS INFORMATION

ADDRESS OF INCIDENT

LOCAL ED CONTACT INFORMATION
ADDRESS
NUMBER

LOCAL LEVEL ONE HOSPITAL CONTACT INFORMATION
ADDRESS
NUMBER

MALIGNANT HYPERTHERMIA HOTLINE CONTACT

**JOHN HOPKINS NURSING EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE LEVEL QUALITY
GUIDELINE**

<p>Level I</p> <p>Experimental study, RCT, Systematic reviews of RCT's with or without meta-analysis</p>	<p>A. High Quality - Consistent, generalizable results, sufficient sample size for this study design, adequate control, definitive conclusions, consistent recommendations based on comprehensive literature review that includes thorough reference to scientific evidence</p>
<p>Level II</p> <p>Quasi-experimental, Systematic review of a combination of RCT's and quasi-experimental studies only, with or without meta-analysis</p>	<p>B. Good Quality- Reasonably consistent results, sufficient sample size for the study design, some control, fairly definitive conclusions, reasonably consistent recommendations based on fairly comprehensive literature review that includes some reference to scientific evidence</p>
<p>Level III</p> <p>Non-experimental study, Systematic review of a combination of RCT's, quasi-experimental and non-experimental studies, or non-experimental studies only with or without meta-analysis</p> <p>Qualitative study or systematic review with or without a meta-analysis</p>	<p>C. Low quality or major flaws - Little evidence with inconsistent results, insufficient sample size for the study design, conclusions cannot be drawn</p>
<p>Level IV</p> <p>Opinion of the respected authorities and/ or nationally recognized expert committees/consensus panels based on scientific evidence</p> <p>Includes Clinical practice guidelines Consensus panels</p>	<p>A. High Quality - Material officially sponsored by a professional, public, private organization, or government agency, documentation of a systematic literature search strategy, consistent results with sufficient numbers of well-designed studies, criteria-based evidence of overall scientific strength and quality of included studies and definitive conclusions, national expertise is clearly evident, developed or revised within the last 5 years</p> <p>B. Good quality - Material officially sponsored by a professional, public</p>
	<p>private organization, or government agency, reasonably thorough and appropriate systematic literature search strategy, reasonably consistent results, sufficient numbers of well-designed studies, evaluation of strengths and limitations</p>

	of included studies with fairly definitive conclusions, national expertise is clearly evident, developed or revised within the last 5 years
	C. Material not sponsored by an official organization or agency, undefined, poorly defined or limited literature search strategy, no evaluation of strengths and limitations of included studies, insufficient evidence with inconsistent results, conclusions cannot be drawn, not revised within the last 5 years
Level V	Organizational Experience
Based on experiential and non-research evidence Includes Literature reviews QI, program or financial evaluation Case reports Opinion of nationally recognized experts based on experiential evidence	A. High quality -Clear aims and objectives, consistent results across multiple settings, formal quality improvement, financial or program evaluation methods used, definitive conclusions, consistent recommendations with thorough reference to scientific evidence
	B. Good quality -Clear aims and objectives, consistent results in a single setting, formal quality improvement or financial or program evaluation methods used, reasonably consistent recommendations with some references to scientific evidence
	C. Low quality or major flaws -Unclear or missing aims and objectives, inconsistent results, poorly defined quality improvement, financial or program evaluation methods, recommendations cannot be made
Literature Review, Expert Opinion, Case Report, Community Standard, Clinical Experience, Consumer Preference (Level V)	A. High quality -Expertise is clearly evident, draws definitive conclusions, provides scientific rationale, thought leaders in the field
	B. Good quality - Expertise appears to be credible, draws fairly definitive conclusions, provides logical argument for opinions
	C. Low quality or major flaws - Expertise is not discernable or is dubious, conclusions cannot be drawn

ANESTHESIA INFORMED CONSENT CHECKLIST

- I have verified with the correct patient identifier and date included on the form
- I have used a qualified interpreter if appropriate
- I have explained the type of restoration needed to treat patient
- I have explained the type of anesthesia available
- I have explained the consequences of refusal of treatment
- I have explained the risks of anesthesia- Aspiration and airway irritation specifically
- I have answered all questions and documented consent
- Parent/Guardian has demonstrated the understanding of the anesthetic explanation of treatment

**PRE-TEST CRITICAL EVENTS TESTING FOR
DENTAL ASSISTANTS AND REGISTERED NURSES**

1. Where are the crash carts located?
2. What is the correct position for a possible aspiration?
3. What is the first action to be taken by dental assistant in case of an airway fire?
4. In the event of an airway fire, what is the first priority the registered nurse has?
5. What is the first sign of an anaphylaxis reaction?
6. What is the primary cause of cardiac arrest in ASA I and II pediatric patients?
7. What is the first thing to do in case of suspected anaphylaxis?
8. What are two actions for managing an airway fire?
9. Which action (s) is/are performed by operating room personnel during a critical event? Circle all that are correct.
 - a. Continue with surgery
 - b. Finish the current procedure
 - c. Hold the next patient until all patients are safe
10. Which type of heart rate is a sign of severe hypoxia?
 - a. increased
 - b. decreased

POST-TEST FOR CRITICAL EVENT TRAINING

1. Hypoxia in the pediatric patient can be identified by which type of heart rate?
 - a. increased
 - b. decreased

2. Identify two components necessary for an airway fire to occur.

3. A primary cause of cardiac arrest in the pediatric patient is....?

4. In the case of an allergic reaction what is the first thing to do?

5. Crash carts are located where?

6. In the event of an airway fire the dental assistant should.....?

7. What is an RN's priority in the case of an airway fire?

8. How should a patient with suspected aspiration be positioned?

9. In the event of a critical event what should the other procedural room do to assist?

10. What are the signs of anaphylaxis?

CRITICAL EVENT SIMULATION EVALUATION

1. What was the most informational portion of the critical events training?
2. What did you like most about the training?
3. What did you like least?
4. What can be improved upon?
5. Additional comments

APPENDIX B

INITIAL LITERATURE SEARCH FOR PEDIATRIC DENTAL ANESTHESIA

Topic	Search Terms # Found	Secondary Terms # Found
Pediatric anesthesia airways	Airways Outpatient anesthesia- One Search 376 PubMed 49 CINAHL 19	Pediatric airway dental anesthesia- One Search 47 PubMed 39 CINAHL 0
Procedural Sedation	Pediatric dental sedation-: One Search 959 PubMed 211 CINAHL 38	
Guidelines- Practice	Anesthesia guidelines- One Search 65,056 PubMed 2,887 CINAHL 9	Pediatric anesthesia guidelines One Search 8,640 PubMed 353 CINAHL 1
Safety	Simulation training- One Search 88,860 PubMed 9,967 CINAHL 559	OR and Anesthesia Simulation training- One Search 1,398 PubMed 465 CINAHL 1
	Quality Management Tools- One Search 230,605 PubMed 8608imor CINAHL 98	Quality Management Anesthesia Tools One Search 6,892 PubMed 29 CINAHL 0
	Just Culture- One Search 1,112,754 PubMed 215,558 CINAHL 48	OR and Just Culture- One Search 44,098 PubMed 329 CINAHL 3
	Debriefing Nursing- One Search 4,509 PubMed 468 CINAHL 0	Debriefing Critical Events One Search 1,444 PubMed 329 CINAHL 0

Topic	Search Terms # Found	Secondary Terms # Found
	Pediatric Anesthesia Critical Events- One Search 3,709 PubMed 159 CINAHL 0	
	Anesthesia Safety- One Search 50,054 PubMed 5,285 CINAHL 20	Pediatric Anesthesia Safety- One Search 8,790 PubMed 616 CINAHL 3

APPENDIX C

JOHN HOPKINS NURSING EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE LEVEL
QUALITY GUIDELINES

<p>Level I</p> <p>Experimental study, RCT, Systematic reviews of RCT's with or without meta-analysis</p>	<p>A. High Quality - Consistent, generalizable results, sufficient sample size for this study design, adequate control, definitive conclusions, consistent recommendations based on comprehensive literature review that includes thorough reference to scientific evidence</p>
<p>Level II</p> <p>Quasi-experimental, Systematic review of a combination of RCT's and quasi-experimental studies only, with or without meta-analysis</p>	<p>B. Good Quality- Reasonably consistent results, sufficient sample size for the study design, some control, fairly definitive conclusions, reasonably consistent recommendations based on fairly comprehensive literature review that includes some reference to scientific evidence</p>
<p>Level III</p> <p>Non-experimental study, Systematic review of a combination of RCT's, quasi-experimental and non-experimental studies, or non-experimental studies only with or without meta-analysis</p> <p>Qualitative study or systematic review with or without a meta-analysis</p>	<p>C. Low quality or major flaws - Little evidence with inconsistent results, insufficient sample size for the study design, conclusions cannot be drawn</p>
<p>Level IV</p> <p>Opinion of the respected authorities and/ or nationally recognized expert committees/consensus panels based on scientific evidence</p> <p>Includes Clinical practice guidelines Consensus panels</p>	<p>A. High Quality - Material officially sponsored by a professional, public, private organization, or government agency, documentation of a systematic literature search strategy, consistent results with sufficient numbers of well-designed studies, criteria-based evidence of overall scientific strength and quality of included studies and definitive conclusions, national expertise is clearly evident, developed or revised within the last 5 years</p> <p>B. Good quality - Material officially sponsored by a professional, public</p>

	private organization, or government agency, reasonably thorough and appropriate systematic literature search strategy, reasonably consistent results, sufficient numbers of well-designed studies, evaluation of strengths and limitations of included studies with fairly definitive conclusions, national expertise is clearly evident, developed or revised within the last 5 years
	C. Material not sponsored by an official organization or agency, undefined, poorly defined or limited literature search strategy, no evaluation of strengths and limitations of included studies, insufficient evidence with inconsistent results, conclusions cannot be drawn, not revised within the last 5 years
Level V	Organizational Experience
Based on experiential and non-research evidence Includes Literature reviews QI, program or financial evaluation Case reports Opinion of nationally recognized experts based on experiential evidence	A. High quality -Clear aims and objectives, consistent results across multiple settings, formal quality improvement, financial or program evaluation methods used, definitive conclusions, consistent recommendations with thorough reference to scientific evidence
	B. Good quality -Clear aims and objectives, consistent results in a single setting, formal quality improvement or financial or program evaluation methods used, reasonably consistent recommendations with some references to scientific evidence
	C. Low quality or major flaws -Unclear or missing aims and objectives, inconsistent results, poorly defined quality improvement, financial or program evaluation methods, recommendations cannot be made
Literature Review, Expert Opinion, Case Report, Community Standard, Clinical	A. High quality -Expertise is clearly evident, draws definitive conclusions,
Experience, Consumer Preference (Level V)	provides scientific rationale, thought leaders in the field

	B. Good quality - Expertise appears to be credible, draws fairly definitive conclusions, provides logical argument for opinions
	C. Low quality or major flaws - Expertise is not discernable or is dubious, conclusions cannot be drawn

APPENDIX D**CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY LONG BEACH
INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD APPROVAL****CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH
OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS**

DATE: June 17, 2019

TO: Mary Wilson
FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1450701-1] Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guidelines for an Ambulatory Surgery Center

REFERENCE #: 19-390

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF NOT HUMAN SUBJECT RESEARCH

DECISION DATE: June 17, 2019

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has determined this project does not meet the definition of human subject research under the purview of the IRB according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

If you have any questions, please contact Mary Walker at (562) 985-5314 or Mary.Walker@csulb.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

APPENDIX E

INDIO SURGERY CENTER SITE APPROVAL

Mary A. Wilson MSN CRNA
California State University, Fullerton
800 N. State College Blvd.
Fullerton, Ca, 928331-3599

February 19, 2019

Board of Directors
Indio Surgery Center
46900 Monroe St., Suite B201
Indio, Ca 92201

We, as the representatives for Indio Surgery Center, do approve the development, implementation and evaluation of the fore-mentioned Quality Improvement (QI) project. This project to be executed by Mary A. Wilson CRNA, MSN, a current Doctorate of Nursing Practice student as California State University Fullerton.

We acknowledge that as a Doctorate dissemination is required for this terminal degree, publication of said QI project is necessary.

X _____ *Mary A. Wilson MSN CRNA*
Date _____ *2/18/19*

APPENDIX F

DELPHI METHOD PDAG EVALUATION PROCESS

APPENDIX G

LESSON PLAN FOR SIMULATION TRAINING (BILLINGS & HALSTEAD, 2019)

Objectives: Staff will demonstrate basic knowledge of airway fires, anaphylaxis, and aspiration critical events

Staff Support: Just culture will be used to increase the level of staff willingness to participate in the simulation training

Problem-Solving: Anesthesia educator will encourage problem solving and teamwork

Guided reflection: Debriefing will be conducted post simulation training and evaluation form will be given to staff.

APPENDIX H

RELIABILITY OF THE EVIDENCE

Leveling and Qualifying the Evidence

Reviewed by 2 DNP prepared CRNAs

Background Literature

1. Guarnizo-Herreno, C. C., & Wehby, G. L. (2012). Children's dental health, school performance, and psychosocial well-being. *The Journal of Pediatrics, 161*(6), 1153–1159. doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2012.05.025 (Level of evidence III, Quality B).
2. Sen, B., Blackburn, J., Morrissey, M. A., Kilgore, M. L., Becker, D. J., Caldwell, C., & Menachemi, N. (2013). Effectiveness of preventive dental visits in reducing nonpreventive dental visits and expenditures. *Pediatrics, 131*(6), 1107–1113. (Level of evidence III, Quality A).
3. Achembong, L. N., Kranz, A. M., & Rozier, R. G. (2014). Office based preventative dental program and statewide trends in dental caries. *Pediatrics, 133*(4), e827–e834. doi.org/10.1542/peds.2013-2561 (Level of evidence III, Quality B).
4. The Dental Board of California. (2016). *Pediatric anesthesia study*. Retrieved from www.dbc.ca.gov/formspubs/pedanesthesiastudy.pdf (Level of evidence IV, Quality A)
5. Cote, C. J., & Wilson, S. (2016). Guidelines for monitoring and management of pediatric patients before, during and after sedation for diagnostic and therapeutic procedures: Update 2016. *American Academy of Pediatrics, 138*(1), e1–e31. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2016-1212> (Level of evidence IV, Quality A).

6. Spera, A. L., Saxen, M. A., Yepes, J. F., Jones, J. E., & Sanders, B. J. (2017). Office-based anesthesia: Safety and outcomes in pediatric dental patients. *Anesthesia Progress*, 64(3), 144–152. doi.org/10.2344/anpr-64-04-05 (Level of evidence III, Quality B).

Evidence-Based Practice Literature

7. Institute for Johns Hopkins Nursing. (2017). *John Hopkins nursing evidence-based practice clinical-decision making tool*. Retrieved from: <https://www.ijhn-education.org/content/johns-hopkins-nursing-evidence-based-practice-model-and-tools> (Level of evidence IV, Quality A).

Assessment, Consent and Parental Information Literature

8. Firdouse, M., Wajchandler, A., Koyle, M., & Fecteau, A. (2017). Checklist to improve informed consent process in pediatric surgery: a pilot study. *Journal of Pediatric Surgery*, 52, 859-863. doi.org/10.1016/j.jpedsurg.2017.01.023 (Level of evidence III, Quality B).
9. Oaks, S. N., Dave, N.M., Garasia, M. B., & Parelkar, S. V. (2015). Surgical checklist application and its impact on patient safety in pediatric surgery. *Journal of Post-graduate Medicine*, 61(2), 92-94. doi:10.4103/0022-3859.150450 (Level of evidence III, Quality B).

Critical Event Training and Curriculum Literature

10. Watkins, S. C., Anders, S., Clebone, A., Hughes, E., Zeigler, L., Patel, V., Shi, Y., Shotwell, M. S., McEvoy, M., Weinger, M. B. (2016). Paper or plastic? Simulation based evaluation of two versions of a cognitive aid for managing pediatric peri-operative critical events by anesthesia trainees; evaluation of the society for

pediatric anesthesia emergency checklist. *Journal of Clinical Monitoring and Computing*, 30, 275-283. doi: 10.1007/s10877-015-9714-7 (Level of evidence III, Quality B)

11. Dekker, S. W. A., Brealey, H. (2016). Just culture: improving safety by achieving substantive, procedural and restorative justice. *Safety Science*, 85, 187-193. doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2016.01.018 (Level V, Quality A).
12. McCall, J. R., Pruchnicki, S. (2017). Just culture: a case study of accountability relationship boundaries influence on safety in High-consequence industries. *Safety Science*, 94, 143-151. doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2017.01.008 (Level V, Quality A).
13. Dekker, S. (2016). *Just culture: balancing safety and accountability* (2nd ed.). London, England: CRC Press. (Level of evidence V, Quality A).
14. Arriaga, A. F., Sweeney R. E., Clapp J. T., Muralidharan, M., & Burson, I. (2019). Failure to debrief after critical events in anesthesia is associated with failures in communication during the event. *Anesthesiology*. doi:10.1097/ALN.0000000000002649 (Level of evidence III, Quality A)

Triage to Higher Level of Care Literature

15. Farrohknia, N., Castren, M., Ehrenberg, A, Lind, L., Oredsson, S., Jonsson, H., Asplund, K., & K. E. Goransson (2011). Emergency department triage scales and their components: A systematic review of the scientific evidence. *Journal of Trauma, Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine*, 19(42), 1-13. <http://www.sjtrem.com/content/19/1/42> (Level of evidence III, Quality A).

APPENDIX I

EVIDENCE LEVEL QUALITY GUIDELINES

Please utilize the John Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice and score accordingly for your agreement or disagreement with how the articles were graded for their level and quality in the attached document.

John Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice Evidence Level Quality Guidelines

Review of the literature	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2
Article # 1/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 2/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 3/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 4/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 5/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 6/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 7/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 8/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 9/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 10/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 11/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 12/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 13/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 14/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 15/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 16/ Yes =1, No = 2		
Article # 17/ Yes =1, No = 2		

APPENDIX J**DELPHI QUALTIX SURVEY ROUND 1**

Q1 Evidence supports the formalized development and implementation of standardized guidelines as a credible method for reducing mortality and morbidity associated with anesthesia in the outpatient setting. Studies rated as Level of evidence III-V and Quality A & B support the recommendation for the development of this Pediatric Dental Anesthesia Guideline.

Agree (3)

Disagree (4)

Please comment on reason for disagreement

Q2 An anesthesia assessment interview should be conducted by an anesthesia provider or a staff member trained in phone assessments and pre-anesthesia education. Findings from this assessment are recorded on a standardized pre-anesthesia assessment checklist. Utilizing the same but labeled procedural assessment checklist, the anesthesia provider will conduct and record an anesthesia assessment on the day of the procedure for completeness and accuracy. Recommendation for this guideline statement are based on the Level of Evidence III and Quality B.

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please comment on disagreement

Q3 To increase the staff's ability to react appropriately to a critical event, simulation training should be conducted at least every 6 months and recorded for future new staff orientation. This training should be available to all new staff during their orientation phase of employment and conducted by a qualified anesthesia provider. Recommendation for this guideline statement are based on Level of Evidence III and Quality A.

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please comment on disagreement response

Q4 Due to the limited resources available in outpatient procedural areas, triaging to a higher level of care is recommended for the following situations: malignant hyperthermia, hypoxia airway fire, anaphylaxis, suspected pulmonary edema, suspected aspiration, and patients receiving racemic-epinephrine after 3 hours of required observation who continue to have an oxygen saturation below 98%, Unstable patients should be transferred to a level one pediatric trauma center and stable patients transferred to the closest emergency department by an emergency medical system. Establishing relationships with local hospitals and appropriate local trauma centers is recommended. Recommendation is based on Level of evidence I and Quality A.

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please comment on disagreement response

Q5

A quality management checklist for quality improvement will be used for root cause analysis of unanticipated events. Debriefing after all critical events with the use of just culture to assure all members of the team will be heard and concerns addressed. All near misses will be tracked and analyzed for quality care improvement. Recommendation is based on the Level of evidence III -IV and Quality A.

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please comment on disagreement response

Q14 I am in agreement with the quality of the evidence as it is rated in the

a. Background

Agree (19)

Disagree (20)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q15

b. Pre-Anesthesia Consent

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q14 c. Informed Consent

- Agree (1)
- Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q15 d. Parental Information

- Agree (1)
- Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q16 e. Critical Event Training

- Agree (25)
- Disagree (26)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q17 f. Triage to a Higher Level of Care

- Agree (25)
- Disagree (26)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q18 g. Quality Management Checklist

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q19 I am in agreement with the comprehension of evidence as it is rated in the

a. Background literature

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q20 b. Pre-Anesthesia Assessment

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q16 c. Informed Consent

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q17 d. Parental Instruction

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q18 e. Critical Event Training

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q19 f. Triage to a Higher Level of Care

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why>

Q20 g. Quality Management Checklist

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q21 I am in agreement with the feasibility of the evidence as it is rated in the

a. Background literature

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which articles(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q22 b. Pre-Anesthesia Assessment

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q23 c. Informed Consent

- Agree (1)
- Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q24 d. Parental Information

- Agree (1)
- Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q25 e. Critical Event Training

- Agree (1)
- Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q26 f. Triage to a Higher Level of Care

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Q27 g. Quality Management Checklist

Agree (1)

Disagree (2)

Please identify which article(s) you are in disagreement with regarding the rating of the evidence and why.

Provide any additional comments on the guidelines here (e.g. additional research articles or changes in wording). Feedback is welcomed and appreciated.

DELPHI ROUND 2

Q5 To increase the staff's ability to react appropriately to a critical event, simulation training should be conducted on a routine basis and recorded for future new staff orientation. This training should be available to all new staff during their orientation phase of employment and conducted by a qualified anesthesia provider. Recommendation for this guideline statement are based on Level of Evidence III-V and Quality A.

- Agree (1)
- Disagree (2)

Please comment on disagreement response

DELPHI 3RD AND FINAL ROUND

To increase the staff's ability to react appropriately to a critical event, simulation training should be conducted on a routine basis and recorded for future new staff orientation. This training should be available to all new staff during their orientation phase of employment and conducted by a qualified anesthesia provider. Recommendation for this guideline statement are based on Level of Evidence III-V and Quality A.

- Agree (1)
- Disagree (2)

Please comment on disagreement response

The disagreement response was selected because

- There is no need for critical event training in the area of outpatient pediatric dental anesthesia. (1)
- It is not financially reasonable to conduct critical event training in outpatient pediatric dental anesthesia. (2)
- The research does not support critical event training in outpatient pediatric dental anesthesia. (3)

APPENDIX K**ANESTHESIA INFORMED CONSENT CHECKLIST**

- I have verified with the correct patient identifier and date included on the form
- I have used a qualified interpreter if appropriate
- I have explained the type of restoration needed to treat patient
- I have explained the type of anesthesia available
- I have explained the consequences of refusal of treatment
- I have explained the risks of anesthesia- Aspiration and airway irritation specifically
- I have answered all questions and documented consent
- Parent/Guardian has demonstrated the understanding of the anesthetic explanation of treatment

APPENDIX L ANESTHESIA CONSENT

Patient Name: _____

Date of Service: _____

Anesthesia Provider: _____

I understand that

_____ I will need anesthesia services for the dental procedure(s) to be done on the agreed date, and that the type of anesthesia to be used will depend upon the procedure and my physical condition.

_____ Anesthesia is a specialty which manages patients who are rendered unconscious or with diminished response to pain and stress during the dental procedure(s).

_____ During the course of the dental procedure, conditions may require additional or different anesthetic monitoring or techniques, and I consent to the anesthesia provider providing any additional necessary services for my benefit and well-being.

_____ No guarantees have been made by anyone regarding the anesthesia services which I am agreeing to have.

TYPE OF ANESTHESIA AND DEFINITIONS:

D. General Anesthesia

4. Total Intravenous Anesthesia: anesthetic medications are passed through an intravenous catheter into a vein.
5. Endotracheal Anesthesia: anesthetic and respiratory gases are passed through a tube placed in the trachea (windpipe via the nose or mouth).
6. Mask Induction Anesthesia: anesthesia gases are passed through a mask which covers the nose and mouth.

E. Nerve Blocks: dental blocks with anesthetic medications to be administered for post-procedural pain management

F. Monitored Anesthesia Care: includes the monitoring of at least blood pressure, oxygenation, respiration, heart-beat, and mental state, supplementing analgesia as needed.

Risks and Complications may include but not limited to: respiratory complications, intubation, longer stay at the surgery center, possible transfer to a higher level of care, allergic/adverse reaction, aspiration, pneumonia, seizures, brain damage, coma, dental injury, inability to reverse the effects of anesthesia, infection, localized swelling, pain, muscle aches, nausea, ophthalmic (eye) injury, positional nerve injury, recall of sound noise/ speech by others, sore throat and even death.

I have been fully advised and completely understand the alternatives to conscious sedation and general anesthesia. I accept the possible risks, side effects, complications and consequences of anesthesia. I acknowledge the receipt of the pre-operative instructions. It has been explained to me and I understand that there is no warranty and no guarantee as to any result or treatment. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about my child's anesthesia, and I am satisfied with the information provided to me. It is also understood that the anesthesia services are completely independent from the operating dentist's procedure.

I have read and understand the consent for anesthesia. I have had the opportunity to have all my questions answered regarding the risks, benefits and alternatives of anesthesia.

Patient Name _____ Date _____

Parent/Guardian's Name _____ Relationship _____

Food (time) _____ AM/PM Liquid (time) _____ AM/PM

Signature _____ Witness _____

APPENDIX M

PRE-PROCEDURAL PATIENT EDUCATION FOR ANESTHESIA

1. The child must have nothing to eat or drink for 8 hours prior to the arrival at the surgery center. The child must be supervised at all times 8 hours prior to the surgery to assure providers that the child has not had anything by mouth. The risk of aspiration is pneumonia. Aspiration can require antibiotics, hospitalization and even cause death.
2. Actively sick children presenting at the surgery center for surgery will be cancelled after assessment by team. This is due to the high risk of respiratory complications when children are sick, breathing treatments might be necessary. This type of respiratory complication may require a longer stay at the surgery center for the child to be observed and a delayed discharge home. There is always a possibility that when this occurs the child might need to be transferred and admitted to the nearest appropriate hospital for further treatment.
3. If the child snores while sleeping, there is a possibility that the child has enlarged tonsils. These enlarged tonsils can increase the risk of respiratory complications. These complications can result in, breathing treatments, a longer stay at the surgery center for observation, abandonment of the procedure and possible transfer to the nearest hospital for further treatment.
4. If the child wakes up ill or has been ill during the previous 2 weeks, please call the surgery center and inform the staff of the child's illness and reschedule as appropriate.

5. Patients with asthma and have been treated with steroids within the recent 6 months will have a steroid preparation given at the surgery center prior to the administration of anesthesia. Please bring any and all medications the child is currently taking to the surgery center the day of surgery.

APPENDIX N

QUALITY IMPROVEMENT CHECKLIST OF UNANTICIPATED EVENTS

Unanticipated event	Circle possible reasons and action
14. Difficult IV	Additional staff required Case cancelled and time of day noted
15. Incorrect Consent	Administration notified Parents notified
16. Unanticipated intubation in the OR	Reason for intubation and actions taken post intubation
17. PACU greater than 90 minutes	Anesthesia notified Racemic epinephrine given Additional medications given
18. Anesthesia provider intervention in PACU after sign off to PACU nurse	Action of the provider noted
19. Airway fire	Throat pack dry O2 at greater than 3 liters
20. Anaphylaxis reaction	All medication noted
21. Medication error or near miss	Look alike drugs Administration notified
22. Wrong X-rays on wrong patient	Multiple staff in room Notify administration
23. Nausea and vomiting greater than 30 minutes	Bleeding Patient dehydrated Antiemetics given Transferred to ED
24. Bleeding in PACU	Extractions without suturing History of bleeding disorders Surgeon notified Anesthesia notified
25. Day of surgery cancellation	Patient ill Heart murmur Parental decision NPO status Notify administration
26. Unplanned transfer to higher level facility	Aspiration Hypoxia Airway fire Bronchospasm Hospital transferred

APPENDIX O**CRITICAL EVENTS TESTING FOR DENTAL ASSISTANTS
AND REGISTERED NURSES**

11. Where are the crash carts located?
12. What is the correct position for a possible aspiration?
13. What is the first action to be taken by dental assistant in case of an airway fire?
14. In the event of an airway fire, what is the first priority the registered nurse has?
15. What is the first sign of an anaphylaxis reaction?
16. What is the primary cause of cardiac arrest in ASA I and II pediatric patients?
17. What is the first thing to do in case of suspected anaphylaxis?
18. What are two actions for managing an airway fire?
19. Which action (s) is/are performed by operating room personnel during a critical event? Circle all that are correct.
 - d. Continue with surgery
 - e. Finish the current procedure
 - f. Hold the next patient until all patients are safe
20. Which type of heart rate is a sign of severe hypoxia?
 - a. increased
 - b. decreased

APPENDIX P**POSTTEST FOR CRITICAL EVENT TRAINING**

11. Hypoxia in the pediatric patient can be identified by which type of heart rate?
 - a. increased
 - b. decreased

12. Identify two components necessary for an airway fire to occur.

13. A primary cause of cardiac arrest in the pediatric patient is....?

14. In the case of an allergic reaction what is the first thing to do?

15. Crash carts are located where?

16. In the event of an airway fire the dental assistant should.....?

17. What is an RN's priority in the case of an airway fire?

18. How should a patient with suspected aspiration be positioned?

19. In the event of a critical event what should the other procedural room do to assist?

20. What are the signs of anaphylaxis?

APPENDIX R**PEDIATRIC DENTAL ANESTHESIA CRITICAL EVENT TRIAGE AND
TRANSPORT PATHWAYS**

Critical events to be transferred to a higher level of care

- h. Hypoxia
- i. Airway Fire
- j. Anaphylaxis
- k. Malignant hyperthermia
- l. Suspected aspiration
- m. Patients receiving racemic-epinephrine after 3 hours of required observation
and still continues to have an Oxygen Saturation below 98%.
- n. Suspected pulmonary edema

Critical Events Procedural Checklist

- 7. Call for help by RN
- 8. All procedures in other OR suites are halted (when can safely be terminated)
until the critical event has been appropriately managed. All available staff are
to report to the to the area of the critical event.
- 9. Registered nurse manager or designee calls EMS for transport
- 10. Parental information given regarding care
- 11. Anesthesia provider to report to facility accepting patient
- 12. Anesthesia provider to go on transport with unstable patient

TRIAGE PATHWAY FOR AIRWAY FIRE

TRIAGE PATHWAY ASPIRATION**STABLE PATIENT**

INTUBATE

OUTPATIENT ADMINISTRATION NOTIFIES PARENT
REGARDING TRANSPORT TO NEAREST ED BY EMS

ADMINISTRATION NOTIFIES EMS OF TRANSPORT

IF O2 SATURATIONS CONSISTENTLY 100%
MAY EXTUBATE AND PREPARE PATIENT FOR
TRANSPORT TO NEAREST ED FOR CHEST XRAY

ANESTHESIA REPORTS TO ED ACCEPTING PROVIDER

TRIAGE TRANSPORT FOR ANAPHYLAXIS

INTUBATE

OUTPATIENT ADMINISTRATION CONTACTS EMS
NOTIFY PARENTS

TRANSPORT PATIENT TO NEAREST LEVEL ONE HOSPITAL
WITH EMS AND ANESTHESIA PROVIDER

TRIAGE PATHWAY FOR MALIGNANT HYPERTHERMIA

**TRIAGE PATHWAY FOR SUSTAINED HYPOXIA AND OR NEGATIVE
PRESSURE PULMONARY EDEMA**

